

INTRODUCTION OF NONSTANDARD METHODS FOR NUMBER THEORISTS

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Abstract

We provide the nuts and bolts of those nonstandard methods that should be useful to those working in additive/combinatorial number theory.

1. Prelude

In the past few decades, nonstandard methods, as a branch of mathematical logic, have been successfully applied to obtain new results in additive/combinatorial number theory (cf. [BJ, Ji1, Ji2, Ji3, Ji4, Ji5, Ji6, JK, Le1, Le2, Le3, Le4]). Although the nonstandard techniques in these applications are elementary from a nonstandard analyst's point of view, it is extremely difficult for a reader who tries to understand these techniques without basic training in mathematical logic. One of the purposes of this article is to provide the nuts and bolts of this training to those who do not have the logic background so that they can understand the proofs in the papers mentioned above and, hopefully, find new applications of the methods to new problems after reading this article.

In short, nonstandard methods take advantage of “infinitely large” integers existing in a nonstandard model. A nonstandard model is a proper extension of the standard world (or standard model) and possesses the same “first-order” truths as in the standard world. Staying inside the nonstandard model, one may not recognize that the model is nonstandard due to the fact that both the standard and nonstandard model satisfy the same “first-order” truth. But if one looks at the nonstandard model from the outside, then one can see many “infinitely large” integers in it. By working inside and outside of the nonstandard model

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alternately, one can gain insights as well as simplify logical reasoning processes in solving some number theoretic problems.

From the experiences of this author some mathematicians have often had doubts that nonstandard methods bring significant advantages to the standard world. As a consequence they may not believe that it is worthwhile to spend time and energy to learn basic knowledge of nonstandard analysis and mathematical logic.

In fact, there have been many interesting results in the standard world obtained by using nonstandard methods since the creation of the subject by A. Robinson, cf. [Ro]. For example, the work of H. J. Keisler *et al.* on probability and stochastic analysis (cf. [FK], [HK], [Ke], etc.), the work of M. Capiński and N. Cutland on nondeterministic Navier-Stokes equations (cf. [CC1], [CC2], [CC3], etc.), the work of Y. Sun on mathematical economics (cf. [KS], [Su1], [Su2], etc.), and the work of S. Leth and the author on additive/combinatorial number theory mentioned above. These results have not been sufficiently exposed to the general mathematical community as they should have because, in the author's opinion, not enough people are able to pass a hurdle of understanding the language and basic techniques of nonstandard analysis. It seems that mathematicians who did not have a logic course during their graduate studies often become reluctant to learn about logic by themselves later on.

So the author hopes the reader can resist the possible negative influence by some perception that nonstandard methods do not produce new interesting standard theorems, or that all proofs with nonstandard methods can be done without them. As explained before, nonstandard methods do produce new, interesting standard theorems. It is true in principle that a proof of a standard result with nonstandard arguments can be translated into another proof without nonstandard arguments. As the reader will see below, a nonstandard model can be constructed within ZFC, which is the standard system of set theory. However, if one does want to do the translation, one may find that the proof becomes unbearably long, and crucial intuition and insights offered by nonstandard methods are lost.

The main purpose of this article is to introduce the nonstandard methods to number theorists. We illustrate the usefulness of nonstandard methods by the author's recent results. For those published results, we will give references. We will call those unpublished results conjectures even though some of those results have been proved in the author's preprints.

We organize the article in the following three sections. In the first section we construct a nonstandard model and prove some basic principles and fundamentals about that nonstandard model. We will give a few easy nonstandard proofs of some well-known theorems as appetizers. The first section is self-contained. In the second section we introduce the Loeb probability measure and present some of its applications. In the third section we introduce the nonstandard cuts and some of their applications. One theorem in the second section will be proved in detail so that the reader can read it without referring too much from outside sources. The proofs for the rest of the results in the second and third sections will be much less comprehensive for the sake of length.

2. Nonstandard Model

In this section we will do the following: (1) define the standard model; (2) construct a nonstandard model; (3) introduce the first-order formulas and establish a logical relationship between the standard model and the nonstandard model; and (4) derive basic principles and theorems about the nonstandard model. The materials in this section are quite standard. We ask the reader to forgive us for not giving sufficient credits to some theorems considered to be well-known in nonstandard analysis. However, our writing has been strongly influenced by [Li]. The reader can also consult [Go] or [He] for slightly different approaches.

2.1. Standard Model

The standard model contains all mathematical objects under consideration. So for example we want that the standard model contains \mathbb{R} , the set of all real numbers, as well as relations such as \leq and functions such as $+$ and \cdot on it.

Definition 1 *Let \bar{N} be a large enough positive integer. Let*

- $V_0 = \mathbb{R}$,
- $V_{n+1} = V_n \cup \mathcal{P}(V_n)$, and
- $V = \bigcup_{n=0}^{\bar{N}} V_n$.

where $\mathcal{P}(V_n)$ is the collection of all subsets of V_n . The set (V, \in) is called the standard model², where \in is the membership relation.

The reader without training in set theory may be uncomfortable considering, for example, that $+$ is a set in V . In fact $+$ can be identified as a set of ordered triples (a, b, c) where $a, b, c \in \mathbb{R}$ and $a + b = c$. Note that (a, b, c) can be identified as the set $\{\{a\}, \{\{a\}, \{\{b\}, \{b, c\}\}\}\}$. Since $a, b, c \in \mathbb{R} = V_0$, (a, b, c) is an element in V_4 . So $+$ is a subset of V_4 . Therefore, $+$ is an element of V_5 .

Although the commonly used relations and functions such as \leq , $+$, and \cdot are now considered to be sets, we may still write $a \leq b$ instead of $(a, b) \in \leq$, write $a + b = c$ instead of $(a, b, c) \in +$, and write $a \cdot b = c$ instead of $(a, b, c) \in \cdot$.

Exercise 2 (1) *Determine the least positive integer n so that \int is an element of V_n , where \int is the integration operator from the set of all real integrable functions on $[0, 1]$ to \mathbb{R} .*

²In other literature the standard model is often defined to be $V = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} V_n$. We let V be the union of V_n 's for only finitely many n from 0 to \bar{N} because we can then avoid introducing bounded formulas.

(2) Determine the least positive integer n so that $(\mathbb{C}; +, \cdot)$ is an element of V_n , where $(\mathbb{C}; +, \cdot)$ is the complex field. Note that a complex number can be viewed as an ordered pair of real numbers.

Since each mathematical proof contains a finite list of arguments, there are only finitely many mathematical objects involved. Hence, one can pick a large enough \overline{N} so that $V_{\overline{N}}$ contains all of these objects involved. However, \overline{N} may need to be increased next time when some objects we want to consider exist only in V_n for some n greater than the previous \overline{N} . Since we didn't specify the mathematical objects involved and didn't specify the concrete value of \overline{N} , we can pretend that \overline{N} is fixed and works for all of our purposes.

2.2. Construction of Nonstandard Model

We will construct a nonstandard model by taking the ultrapower of the standard model modulo a non-principal ultrafilter on a countable set.

Definition 3 A collection \mathcal{F} of subsets of \mathbb{N} is called a **filter** if the following are true:

1. $\emptyset \notin \mathcal{F}$ and $\mathbb{N} \in \mathcal{F}$,
2. $A \cap B \in \mathcal{F}$ for any $A, B \in \mathcal{F}$,
3. $A \in \mathcal{F}$ and $A \subseteq B$ imply $B \in \mathcal{F}$ for any $A, B \subseteq \mathbb{N}$.

The filter \mathcal{F} is called a **non-principal ultrafilter** if

4. $\{n\} \notin \mathcal{F}$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$,
5. for every $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$, either $A \in \mathcal{F}$ or $\mathbb{N} \setminus A \in \mathcal{F}$.

Note that the collection of all cofinite subsets of \mathbb{N} is a filter, called the Fréchet filter; but it is not an ultrafilter because, for example, neither the set of all even numbers, nor its complement, is cofinite. Let $a \in \mathbb{N}$. The collection of all subsets of \mathbb{N} containing a is a filter and satisfies (5). But it fails (4).

The existence of a non-principal ultrafilter is not trivial. It depends on the axiom of choice. See [Je] for the following theorem. Given a non-principal ultrafilter on \mathbb{N} , one can regard the sets in the ultrafilter as “large” subsets of \mathbb{N} . If we assign 1 for each set in the ultrafilter and 0 for each set not in the ultrafilter, then we have a finitely additive 0-1 measure on the power set of \mathbb{N} .

Theorem 4 (ZFC) *There exists a non-principal ultrafilter on \mathbb{N} .*

In order to construct a non-principal ultrafilter one starts with Fréchet filter \mathcal{F}_0 and then adds, one by one, each subset of \mathbb{N} or its complement to the collection without violating (1), (2), and (3) above. When all subsets of \mathbb{N} are taken care of, the final collection becomes an ultrafilter. One needs the axiom of choice to line up all subsets of \mathbb{N} in a well-ordered fashion so that these sets can be dealt with in a “one-by-one” fashion.

From now on we fix a non-principal ultrafilter \mathcal{F} on \mathbb{N} .

Let $V^{\mathbb{N}}$ be the set of all functions from \mathbb{N} to V . Note that we can view $V^{\mathbb{N}}$ as a proper extension of V by identifying each $a \in V$ with the constant function f_a with single value a . However, we also need the extension to satisfy the same first-order formulas that are satisfied by the standard model. For example, in V it is true that the real numbers are linearly ordered. How can we linearly order all functions in $\mathbb{R}^{\mathbb{N}}$? We can do this by considering $\mathbb{R}^{\mathbb{N}}$ modulo an equivalence relation induced by the ultrafilter. We first define the equivalence relation on $V^{\mathbb{N}}$ modulo \mathcal{F} .

Definition 5 *Given any $f, g \in V^{\mathbb{N}}$, let*

1. $f \sim g$ iff $\{n : f(n) = g(n)\} \in \mathcal{F}$,
2. $[f] = \{g \in V^{\mathbb{N}} : g \sim f\}$,
3. ${}^*V = V^{\mathbb{N}}/\mathcal{F} = \{[f] : f \in V^{\mathbb{N}}\}$, and
4. $[f] {}^*\in [g]$ iff $\{n : f(n) \in g(n)\} \in \mathcal{F}$.

Exercise 6 *Show that “ \sim ” defined above is an equivalence relation.*

Now we have the set *V with the relation ${}^*\in$ on the set. For each $a \in V$ let $f_a \in V^{\mathbb{N}}$ be the constant function with the single value a .

Definition 7 $*$: $V \mapsto {}^*V$ is the map defined by $*(a) = {}^*a = [f_a]$.

Note that $*$ is an embedding of V into *V satisfying $a = b$ iff ${}^*a = {}^*b$ and $a \in b$ iff ${}^*a {}^*\in {}^*b$. So if we identify $a \in V$ with *a in *V , we can view *V as an extension of V . Let’s pretend that $a \in V$ and ${}^*a \in {}^*V$ are the same element. However, the reader should be aware of the difference between a and *a . When $a \in V_0$, there is no problem. But if A is an infinite set in V , then *A contains more elements than those in $\{{}^*a : a \in A\}$. For example, \mathbb{N} in V can be identified with ${}^*\mathbb{N}$ in *V although \mathbb{N} is a proper subset of ${}^*\mathbb{N}$ in *V . It is like a candy bag in two different worlds. Suppose \mathbb{N} is a candy bag in V . If one brings the candy bag into *V , the bag changes its name to ${}^*\mathbb{N}$ and some new candies are added in. So as candy bags they are the same. But in different worlds the same candy bag contains different amounts of candies.

The reader should notice that the relation $^* \in$ is not a true membership relation on *V , but we can pretend it is.³

Exercise 8 Let $A \in V$. Show that $^*A = \{[f] : f \in A^{\mathbb{N}}\}$, i.e., $a \in ^*A$ iff $a = [f]$ for some $f \in A^{\mathbb{N}}$.

Exercise 9 Show that $^* \leq$ is a linear order on $^*\mathbb{R}$.

For convenience we often drop the symbol $*$ when no confusion will result. For example, we often write \in for $^* \in$ in *V . When we write mathematical expressions in the nonstandard model, we often write \leq for $^* \leq$, $+$ for $^*+$, and \cdot for * . When $a \in V_0$, we write a for *a .

Note that $^* : V \mapsto ^*V$ is not a surjection. Let f be the identity function on \mathbb{N} . Then $[f] \in ^*\mathbb{N}$ and for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $[f] > n$. We call $^*\mathbb{N}$ the set of all non-negative integers, $^*\mathbb{Z}$ the set of all integers, and $^*\mathbb{R}$ the set of all real numbers, in *V .

Definition 10

- A set A is called **standard** if $A = [f_a]$ for some $a \in V$.
- A set A is called **internal** if $A = [f] \in ^*V$.
- A set A is called **external** if it is not internal.
- An integer in $^*\mathbb{N} \setminus \mathbb{N}$ is called a **hyperfinite integer**.

$^*\mathbb{N}$ is a standard set, although it contains hyperfinite integers. For a hyperfinite integer $H = [h]$, the set $[0, H] = \{n \in ^*\mathbb{N} : 0 \leq n \leq H\}$ is internal but not standard because $[0, H] = [f]$ where f is a function from \mathbb{N} to V such that $f(n) = [0, h(n)]$ and, the reader will see, $[0, H]$ cannot be standard. The reader will also see that the set \mathbb{N} as a subset of $^*\mathbb{N}$ is an external set.

2.3. First-order Formula

Every mathematical argument can be expressed by a finite sequence of symbols. In our context we need the following symbols plus parentheses “(” and “)”.

³ *V can be embedded into a superstructure on $^*\mathbb{R}$ so that $^* \in$ is transformed into the true membership relation \in under this embedding. The embedding is called Mostowski Collapsing. Consider $^*\mathbb{R} = \mathbb{R}^{\mathbb{N}}/\mathcal{F}$ as a set of atoms. Let $W_0 = ^*\mathbb{R}$, $W_{n+1} = W_n \cup \mathcal{P}(W_n)$, and $W = \bigcup_{n=0}^{\overline{\mathbb{N}}} W_n$. Let $i : ^*V \mapsto W$ be the map such that $i(a) = a$ for every $a \in ^*\mathbb{R}$ and $i(A) = \{i(a) : a \in A\}$ for every $A \in ^*V \setminus ^*\mathbb{R}$. Then i is a one-to-one map and $i(a) \in i(A)$ iff $a \in A$.

- variables: x, y, z, \dots
- parameters: $a, b, c, \dots, A, B, C, \dots$
- logical symbols: $=, \neg, \wedge, \exists x$.
- membership relation symbol: \in

The set FM of all formulas under our consideration is the smallest set such that

1. FM contains all formulas of the form “ $s = t$ ” and “ $s \in t$ ” where s and t can be either variables or parameters. The formulas of the form “ $s = t$ ” and “ $s \in t$ ” are called atomic formulas.
2. if φ is in FM , then $\neg\varphi$ is in FM ,
3. if φ and ψ are in FM , then $\varphi \wedge \psi$ is in FM ,
4. if φ is in FM , then $\exists x\varphi$ is in FM . Here φ is called the scope of $\exists x$.

A variable x is called bounded in φ if x occurs in the scope of some $\exists x$ in φ . A variable x is called free in φ if x is not bounded in φ . A formula φ is called a sentence if φ contains no free variables. For example, the formula “ $x + y = z$ ” is not a sentence and the formula “ $\forall x\forall y\exists z(x + y = z)$ ” is a sentence. We often write $\varphi(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n)$ to indicate that x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k are all free variables occurring in φ and a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n are all parameters occurring in φ .

One may notice that the definition of the set FM is recursive. We define the set of all atomic formulas as the basic level. Then the formulas with higher and higher complexity are added in. The reader may keep in mind that if one wants to prove something about all formulas, it is common to prove by induction on the complexity of the formulas.

In the definition of a formula above we didn't mention the other commonly used symbols such as $\vee, \rightarrow, \forall x$, etc. The formulas using these symbols can be represented by the formulas using the symbols already introduced. For example, $\varphi \vee \psi$ can be represented by $\neg(\neg\varphi \wedge \neg\psi)$, $\varphi \rightarrow \psi$ by $\neg\varphi \vee \psi$, and $\forall x\varphi$ by $\neg\exists x\neg\varphi$.

We assume that the reader can interpret each of the symbols mentioned above into its natural meaning. For example, \neg means “not”, \wedge means “and”, and $\exists x$ means “there exists x so that” The reader should feel free to interpret the other symbols directly instead of interpreting them according to their representations in terms of \neg, \wedge , and $\exists x$. For example, “ \vee ” means “or”, “ \rightarrow ” means “imply”, and “ $\forall x$ ” means “for every x ...”. We do not include \vee, \rightarrow , or $\forall x$, in the definition of formulas because then we can shorten some inductive proofs on formulas later on.

We say that a formula φ is in V ($*V$) if all parameters in φ are from V ($*V$). It is very important to distinguish a first-order formula from a non-first-order formula.

Definition 11 A formula φ in $V (*V)$ is called a first-order formula if $\exists x$ occurring in φ is always interpreted by “there exists an **element** x in $V (*V)$ such that ...”.

Definition 12 Let φ be a first-order sentence in $V (*V)$. We define the truth value of φ in $V (*V)$ inductively as the following.

- Let a, b be in $V (*V)$ and φ be an atomic sentence $a = b$ or $a \in b$. The sentence $a = b$ is true in $V (*V)$ if a and b are the same element. The sentence $a \in b$ is true in $V (*V)$ if $a \in b$ ($a * \in b$).
- If φ is $\neg\psi$, then φ is true in $V (*V)$ iff ψ is false in $V (*V)$.
- If φ is $\psi \wedge \chi$, then φ is true in $V (*V)$ iff ψ is true in $V (*V)$ and χ is true in $V (*V)$.
- If φ is $\exists x\psi(x)$, then φ is true in $V (*V)$ iff there is an element a in $V (*V)$ such that $\psi(a)$ is true in $V (*V)$, where $\psi(a)$ is the sentence obtained by substituting all free occurrences of x in ψ with a .

We use the following examples to indicate the delicate difference between a first-order formula and a non-first-order formula. Let “ $(\exists x \in s)\varphi$ ” be the abbreviation of “ $\exists x (x \in s \wedge \varphi)$,” “ $(\forall x \in s)\varphi$ ” be the abbreviation of “ $\forall x (x \in s \rightarrow \varphi)$,” “ $s \subseteq t$ ” be the abbreviation of “ $\forall x (x \in s \rightarrow x \in t)$,” and “ $(\forall x \subseteq t)\varphi$ ” be the abbreviation of “ $\forall x (x \subseteq t \rightarrow \varphi)$.” Clearly, “ $\forall x \subseteq t$ ” means “for every subset of t .”

Example 13 Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$.

“ $(\exists x \in \mathbb{N})(\forall y \in A)(y \leq x)$ ” is a first-order sentence in V with parameters A, \mathbb{N} , and \leq , which means that “ A is bounded in \mathbb{N} .”

“ $(a \in A) \wedge (\forall x \in A)(x \leq a)$ ” is a first-order sentence in V with parameters a, A , and \leq , which means “ $a = \max A$.”

Example 14 The following are two sentences. If one takes the natural interpretation, one can find that the first sentence is first-order and the second is not.

1. $(\forall X \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N}))(X \text{ is unbounded in } \mathbb{N} \text{ or } X \text{ has a maximal element in } \mathbb{N})$.
2. $(\forall X \subseteq \mathbb{N})(X \text{ is unbounded in } \mathbb{N} \text{ or } X \text{ has a maximal element in } \mathbb{N})$.

Note that “ $\forall X \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N})$ ” in the first sentence means “for all **elements** X of the set $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N})$ ” and “ $\forall X \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ ” in the second sentence means “for all subsets X of \mathbb{N} ,” which is obviously not first-order. However, in our standard world both formulas seem to mean exactly the same thing. The reader will see that these two sentences are different in the nonstandard model if the parameters \mathbb{N} and $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N})$ are replaced by $*\mathbb{N}$ and $*\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N})$. Note that $*\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N})$ and $\mathcal{P}(*\mathbb{N})$ are different.

Exercise 15 Let f be a function from \mathbb{R} to \mathbb{R} and let $a \in \mathbb{R}$. Express the statement “ f is continuous at a ” by a first-order sentence in V . Note that the usual order \leq on \mathbb{R} should appear in the sentence as a parameter.

2.4. Basic Principles, Theorems, and Lemmas

We first show that V and $*V$ satisfy exactly the same set of first-order sentences with parameters from V in the next theorem called the transfer principle.

Theorem 16 Let $\varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ be a first-order sentence in V where a_i 's are all parameters occurring in φ . Then $\varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ is true in V iff $\varphi(*a_1, *a_2, \dots, *a_k)$ is true in $*V$.

The transfer principle is a key to all nonstandard proofs. In fact, whether an extension of the standard model is called a nonstandard model depends on whether it satisfies the transfer principle. However, the proof that the model obtained by the ultrapower construction above satisfies the transfer principle is due to Łos.

We prove a lemma first and show that Theorem 16 follows from the lemma. For simplicity we write \bar{x} for a finite sequence of variables x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k and \bar{a} for a finite sequence of parameters a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n .

Lemma 17 Let $\varphi(\bar{x}, \bar{c})$ be in FM and $\overline{[f]}$ and $\overline{[g]}$ be in $*V$. Then $\varphi(\overline{[f]}, \overline{[g]})$ is true in $*V$ iff $\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \varphi(\overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)})$ is true in $V\} \in \mathcal{F}$.

Proof. We prove the lemma by induction on the complexity of φ .

Suppose φ is an atomic formula $s = t$ or $s \in t$. Then the lemma is true by (1) and (4) of Definition 5.

Suppose $\varphi(\bar{x}, \bar{c})$ is a formula of the form $\neg\psi(\bar{x}, \bar{c})$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(\overline{[f]}, \overline{[g]}) \text{ is true in } *V &\text{ iff} \\ \psi(\overline{[f]}, \overline{[g]}) \text{ is not true in } *V &\text{ iff} \\ \{n \in \mathbb{N} : \psi(\overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} &\notin \mathcal{F} \text{ iff} \\ \{n \in \mathbb{N} : \neg\psi(\overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} &\in \mathcal{F} \text{ iff} \\ \{n \in \mathbb{N} : \varphi(\overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} &\in \mathcal{F}. \end{aligned}$$

Note that in this step the fact that $A \notin \mathcal{F}$ iff $\mathbb{N} \setminus A \in \mathcal{F}$ is used.

Suppose $\varphi(\bar{x}, \bar{c})$ has the form $\psi(\bar{x}, \bar{c}) \wedge \chi(\bar{x}, \bar{c})$. Then

$\varphi(\overline{[f]}, \overline{[g]})$ is true in *V iff

$\psi(\overline{[f]}, \overline{[g]})$ is true in *V and $\chi(\overline{[f]}, \overline{[g]})$ is true in *V iff

$\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \psi(\overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} \in \mathcal{F}$ and

$\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \chi(\overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} \in \mathcal{F}$ iff

$\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \psi(\overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} \cap$

$\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \chi(\overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} \in \mathcal{F}$ iff

$\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \psi(\overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \wedge \chi(\overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} \in \mathcal{F}$ iff

$\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \varphi(\overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} \in \mathcal{F}$.

Suppose $\varphi(\bar{x}, \bar{c})$ has the form $\exists y \psi(y, \bar{x}, \bar{c})$. Then $\varphi(\overline{[f]}, \overline{[g]})$ being true in *V implies that there is $[h]$ in *V such that $\psi(\overline{[h]}, \overline{[f]}, \overline{[g]})$ is true in *V . Here we use the fact that φ is first-order. By induction we have

$$\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \psi(\overline{h(n)}, \overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} \in \mathcal{F}.$$

Since $\psi(\overline{h(n)}, \overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)})$ is true in V implies $\exists y \psi(y, \overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)})$ is true in V , then $\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \exists y \psi(y, \overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} \in \mathcal{F}$.

One the other hand, let

$$X = \{n \in \mathbb{N} : \exists y \psi(y, \overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} \in \mathcal{F}.$$

Then for each $n \in X$ there is $h(n) \in V$ such that

$$\psi(\overline{h(n)}, \overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V.$$

Let $h(n) = 0$ for every $n \notin X$. Then

$$\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \psi(\overline{h(n)}, \overline{f(n)}, \overline{g(n)}) \text{ is true in } V\} \in \mathcal{F}.$$

So $\psi(\overline{[h]}, \overline{[f]}, \overline{[g]})$ is true in *V . Hence $\exists y \psi(y, \overline{[f]}, \overline{[g]})$ is true in *V . This ends the proof.

Proof of Theorem 16. Since $*a_i = [f_{a_i}]$ and $f_{a_i}(n) = a_i$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then $\varphi(*a_1, *a_2, \dots, *a_k)$ is true in $*V$ iff

$$\{n \in \mathbb{N} : \varphi(f_{a_1}(n), f_{a_2}(n), \dots, f_{a_k}(n)) \text{ is true in } V\} \in \mathcal{F}$$

iff $\varphi(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ is true in V .

There are many different ways to construct a nonstandard model. The ultrapower construction mentioned above is just one of the ways. We choose the ultrapower construction because we want to minimize the use of mathematical logic.

We now use the transfer principle to prove some basic facts.

Theorem 18 $*\leq$ on $*\mathbb{N}$ is a linear order.

Proof. The sentence “ \leq is a linear order on \mathbb{N} ” is a true first-order sentence in V . By Theorem 16 the sentence “ $*\leq$ is a linear order on $*\mathbb{N}$ ” is true in $*V$.

Theorem 19 (1) Let $[f] \in *\mathbb{N}$ and $[f] \leq n$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Then $[f] = k$ for some non-negative standard integer $k \leq n$. This shows all hyperfinite integers are greater than all standard positive integers. (2) For every finite set A in V , $[f] \in *A$ implies $[f] = *a$ for some $a \in A$. This shows that for a finite set A in V , $*A = \{ *a : a \in A \}$.

Proof. (1) Let $n \in \mathbb{N}$. The following sentence “ $(\forall x \in \mathbb{N})(x \leq n \rightarrow (x = 0 \wedge x = 1 \wedge \dots \wedge x = n))$ ” is true in V . Hence “ $(\forall x \in *\mathbb{N})(x \leq n \rightarrow (x = 0 \wedge x = 1 \wedge \dots \wedge x = n))$ ” is true in $*V$. The proof of (2) is the same.

Example 20 The first-order sentence “ $(\forall X \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N}))(X \text{ is unbounded in } \mathbb{N} \text{ or } X \text{ has a maximal element in } \mathbb{N})$ ” is true in V . Hence “ $(\forall X \in *\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N}))(X \text{ is unbounded in } *\mathbb{N} \text{ or } X \text{ has a maximal element in } *\mathbb{N})$ ” is true in $*V$.

Example 21 The formula “ $(\forall X \subseteq \mathbb{N})(X \text{ is unbounded in } \mathbb{N} \text{ or } X \text{ has a maximal element in } \mathbb{N})$ ” is true in V . But the formula “ $(\forall X \subseteq *\mathbb{N})(X \text{ is unbounded in } *\mathbb{N} \text{ or } X \text{ has a maximal element in } *\mathbb{N})$ ” is false in $*V$. The fallacy is exemplified by \mathbb{N} because \mathbb{N} is an upper bounded subset of $*\mathbb{N}$ and does not have a maximal element.

Example 22 Note that $*\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{N})$ is the set of all internal subsets of \mathbb{N} and $\mathcal{P}(*\mathbb{N})$ is the set of all subsets of $*\mathbb{N}$. So every bounded internal subset of $*\mathbb{N}$ has a maximal element. Hence \mathbb{N} is an external subset of $*\mathbb{N}$.

The transfer principle can also be used to derive some useful lemmas. The next lemma is called the lemma of internal definition. Roughly speaking, if a set is defined in a nonstandard model by a first-order formula with internal parameters, then the set is internal.

Lemma 23 *Let $\varphi(x, \bar{y})$ be a first-order formula without parameters. Let A and \bar{b} be internal. Then the set*

$$S = \{a \in A : \varphi(a, \bar{b}) \text{ is true in } {}^*V\}$$

is internal.

Proof. Let $\varphi(x, \bar{y})$ be the first-order sentence

$$“\forall z \forall \bar{y} \exists u (u \subseteq z \wedge \forall x (x \in u \leftrightarrow (x \in z \wedge \varphi(x, \bar{y}))))”.$$

Then φ is true in V . Hence it is true in *V . Let z take value A and \bar{y} take value \bar{b} . Then the witness for u is the internal set S we want.

Corollary 24 *Let $U \subseteq {}^*\mathbb{N}$ be a non-empty initial segment, i.e., $m < n$ and $n \in U$ imply $m \in U$, and U is external. (1) If X is internal and $U \cap X$ is upper unbounded in U , then there is $a \in X \setminus U$. (2) If X is internal and $X \setminus U$ is lower unbounded in ${}^*\mathbb{N} \setminus U$, then there is $a \in X \cap U$.*

Proof. (1) Suppose $X \setminus U = \emptyset$. Then $x \in U$ if and only if $\exists y \in X (x \leq y)$. Hence U can be defined by a first-order formula with parameters X and \leq . By Lemma 23, U is internal, which contradicts that U is external. The proof of (2) is symmetric.

Lemma 25 *Let $S = \langle a_n \in \mathbb{R} : n \in \mathbb{N} \rangle$ be a standard sequence in V . Then S can be extended to a nonstandard sequence ${}^*S = \langle {}^*a_n : n \in {}^*\mathbb{N} \rangle$ in *V .*

Proof. We can view S as a function from \mathbb{N} to \mathbb{R} . Given any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and let $S(n) = a_n$. The sentence “ S is a function from \mathbb{N} to \mathbb{R} and $S(n) = a_n$ ” is true in V . By the transfer principle the sentence “ *S is a function from ${}^*\mathbb{N}$ to ${}^*\mathbb{R}$ and ${}^*S(n) = {}^*a_n$ ” is true in *V .

The next theorem is called countable saturation. It is not a consequence of the transfer principle, but a property from the ultrapower construction. The theorem has a fundamental importance. It offers greater convenience in nonstandard methods. Since Theorem 26 is needed in many proofs, we will only refer to it a couple of times to avoid annoying the reader.

Theorem 26 *If A_k for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ is a nonempty internal set such that $A_0 \supseteq A_1 \supseteq A_2 \supseteq \dots$, then $\bigcap_{k \in \mathbb{N}} A_k \neq \emptyset$.*

Proof. We need to find an element v in *V such that $v \in A_k$ for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$. Since A_k is internal, we can find a function $F_k \in V^{\mathbb{N}}$ such that $A_k = [F_k]$ for each k . For each k choose $a_k \in A_k$ and let $a_k = [v_k]$ where $v_k \in V^{\mathbb{N}}$.

By Lemma 17 we have that

$$U_k = \{n \in \mathbb{N} : n > k \text{ and } v_k(n) \in F_k(n) \subseteq F_{k-1}(n) \subseteq \dots \subseteq F_0(n)\} \in \mathcal{F}$$

for each k . Clearly $U_0 \supseteq U_1 \supseteq U_2 \supseteq \dots$ and $\bigcap_{k \in \mathbb{N}} U_k = \emptyset$. For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ define $k_n = \max\{k : n \in U_k\}$. Now we define the function $v : \mathbb{N} \mapsto V$ by

$$v(n) = v_{k_n}(n).$$

We need to show $[v] \in [F_k]$ for each k . Fix k . It suffices to show

$$U_k \subseteq \{n \in \mathbb{N} : v(n) \in F_k(n)\}.$$

Let $n \in U_k$. Then we have $k \leq k_n$ and $n \in U_{k_n}$ by the definition of k_n . Hence $v(n) = v_{k_n}(n) \in F_{k_n}(n) \subseteq \dots \subseteq F_k(n) \subseteq \dots \subseteq F_0(n)$ by the definition of U_{k_n} . In particular, $v(n) \in F_k(n)$. This ends the proof.

Corollary 27 *Let $\{H_k : k \in \mathbb{N}\}$ be a set of hyperfinite integers. Then there is a hyperfinite integer N such that $N < H_k$ for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$.*

Proof. For each k let $K_k = \min\{H_i : i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k\}$ and let $A_k = [k, K_k - 1]$. For each k , A_k is internal and $A_k \supseteq A_{k+1}$. By Theorem 26 there is $N \in \bigcap_{k \in \mathbb{N}} A_k$. N is clearly hyperfinite and less than every H_k .

Exercise 28 *Suppose $\{a_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ and $\{b_n : n \in \mathbb{N}\}$ are two sequences of integers in *V such that $a_0 < a_1 < a_2 < \dots < b_2 < b_1 < b_0$. Show that there is an integer c such that $a_0 < a_1 < a_2 < \dots < c < \dots < b_2 < b_1 < b_0$.*

Corollary 29 *Let $f : \mathbb{N} \mapsto {}^*\mathbb{R}$ be an (external) function. Then there is a hyperfinite integer H and an internal function $F : [0, H] \mapsto {}^*\mathbb{R}$ such that for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we have $F(n) = f(n)$.*

Proof. For each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ let X_k be the set of all internal functions F_k such that $F_k(n) = f(n)$ for all $n = 0, 1, \dots, k$. So X_k is a nonempty internal set and $X_k \supseteq X_{k+1}$. By Theorem 26 we can find $F \in \bigcap_{k \in \mathbb{N}} X_k$. Now F is internal so its domain is also internal. $F(n) = f(n)$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ due to the choice of X_k . Hence the domain of F contains all standard non-negative integers. So the domain of F contains $[0, H]$ for some hyperfinite integer H .

In order to keep the reading interesting we would like to give the reader a taste of nonstandard methods by presenting simple nonstandard proofs of two well-known theorems

in combinatorial number theory. We do not claim that these nonstandard proofs are simpler than usual standard proofs.

König’s Lemma *Suppose T is an infinite tree. Suppose also that each level of T is finite. Then T must have an infinite path.*

Proof. We can assume $T = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} T_n$ where T_n is the n -th level of T . Then ${}^*T = \bigcup_{n \in {}^*\mathbb{N}} {}^*T_n$. Note that ${}^*T_n = T_n$ for every standard n because T_n is finite. Since each level T_n is nonempty in V , then *T_n is nonempty for each $n \in {}^*\mathbb{N}$. Let H be a hyperfinite integer and $t_H \in {}^*T_H$. Then $\{t \in T : t \leqslant_{{}^*T} t_H\}$ is an infinite path of T .

For a set A let $[A]^2$ be the set $\{\{a, b\} : a, b \in A \text{ and } a \neq b\}$.

Ramsey’s Theorem for pairs *Given $f : [\mathbb{N}]^2 \mapsto \{0, 1\}$, there is an infinite set $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that f is a constant function on $[A]^2$.*

*Proof.*⁴ Suppose the theorem is not true. Let H be a hyperfinite integer. For $i = 0, 1$, let $A_i \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be maximal such that ${}^*f \upharpoonright [A_i \cup \{H\}]^2 \equiv i$. Note that A_i must be finite for $i = 0, 1$ by the initial assumption. Since the first-order sentence “there is x in ${}^*\mathbb{N} \setminus (A_0 \cup A_1)$ such that ${}^*f \upharpoonright [A_i \cup \{x\}]^2 \equiv i$ ” is true in *V , then, by the transfer principle, the sentence “there is $c \in \mathbb{N} \setminus (A_0 \cup A_1)$ such that $f \upharpoonright [A_i \cup \{c\}]^2 \equiv i$ ” is true in V . If ${}^*f(c, H) = i$ for $i = 0$ or 1 , then A_i can be replaced by $A_i \cup \{c\}$, which contradicts the maximality of A_i .

At this moment we would like to make two important comments on nonstandard methods. (1) By the definition of the nonstandard model above it is tempting for the reader to always consider an internal element as a sequence of standard elements. This may be helpful when the reader is at the learning stage and trying to grasp basic concepts and principles. However, thinking of an internal object as a sequence of standard objects is a costly habit. If the reader picks up this habit, he/she may quickly clog his/her mind with these sequences and lose some insight and intuition. Imagine, for example, how calculus would become if one had always thought of a real number as a Cauchy sequence of rational numbers. (2) One cannot take advantage of nonstandard methods in deriving interesting theorems in the standard model if he/she uses internal arguments in *V only. By the transfer principle, an internal argument involving only standard objects can always be translated into a standard argument. On the other hand, internal arguments should not be avoided because otherwise we merely work like a set theorist. In order to take advantage of nonstandard methods we should use internal and external arguments alternately so that the advantages of both sides can be mixed together to produce surprising results in the standard model.

⁴The author learned the proof of Ramsey’s Theorem from A. Miller when the author was a graduate student at the University of Wisconsin and took a model theory class from Professor Miller.

When we quantify over the set of all hyperfinite integers we use an external argument. When we quantify over the set of all standard real numbers in *V we use an external argument. We will introduce more external tools for nonstandard methods. The standard part map is an external tool, which connects the standard model and nonstandard model in a natural way.

2.5. Standard Part Map

Definition 30 Let $r, s \in {}^*\mathbb{R}$.

- $r \approx 0$ iff $|r| < \frac{1}{n}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.
- $r \approx s$ iff $r - s \approx 0$.
- $Fin({}^*\mathbb{R}) = \{r \in {}^*\mathbb{R} : |r| < n \text{ for some } n \in \mathbb{N}\}$.

A real number r in ${}^*\mathbb{R}$ is called an infinitesimal if $r \approx 0$. The following theorem is an equivalent form of the least upper bound axiom.

Theorem 31 For each $r \in Fin({}^*\mathbb{R})$ there is a unique $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $r \approx \alpha$.

Proof. Let $S = \{\beta \in \mathbb{R} : \beta < r\}$. Then S is non-empty and upper bounded in \mathbb{R} . By the least upper bound axiom S has a least upper bound α in \mathbb{R} . It is now an easy exercise to prove that $r \approx \alpha$ and α is unique.

Exercise 32 Finish the proof of Theorem 31, i.e., prove that $r \approx \alpha$ and α is unique.

Definition 33 The standard part map is the function $st : Fin({}^*\mathbb{R}) \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ such that $st(r) = \alpha$ iff $r \approx \alpha$.

Theorem 34 Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$. A function $f : \mathbb{R} \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ is continuous at α iff for every $r \in {}^*\mathbb{R}$, $st(r) = \alpha$ implies $st({}^*f(r)) = f(\alpha)$.

Proof. “ \Rightarrow ” Assume f is continuous at α , $r \in {}^*\mathbb{R}$ and $r \approx \alpha$. Given $n \in \mathbb{N}$, we want to show $|{}^*f(r) - f(\alpha)| < \frac{1}{n}$. Let $\varphi(\delta, n, \mathbb{R})$ be the formula

$$(\forall x \in \mathbb{R}) \left(|x - \alpha| < \delta \rightarrow |f(x) - f(\alpha)| < \frac{1}{n} \right)$$

and let $\delta > 0$ be a standard real number such that $\varphi(\delta, n, \mathbb{R})$ is true in V . By the transfer principle $\varphi(\delta, n, {}^*\mathbb{R})$ is true in *V . Since $|r - \alpha| < \delta$ is true, $|{}^*f(r) - f(\alpha)| < \frac{1}{n}$ is true.

“ \Leftarrow ” Suppose f is not continuous at α . Fix a standard $\epsilon > 0$ and a standard sequence $\langle x_n : n \in \mathbb{N} \rangle$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = \alpha \text{ and } |f(x_n) - f(\alpha)| \geq \epsilon$$

for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Let H be an hyperfinite integer. By the transfer principle, we can show that $x_H \approx \alpha$ and $|{}^*f(x_H) - f(\alpha)| \geq \epsilon$. Hence $st(x_H) = \alpha$ but $st({}^*f(x_H)) \neq f(\alpha)$.

We learned the following nonstandard proof of a theorem in calculus from [Li].

Extreme Value Theorem *If $f : [0, 1] \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ is continuous, then there is $c \in [0, 1]$ such that $f(c) = \sup \{f(x) : 0 \leq x \leq 1\}$.*

Proof. Working in *V . Let H be a hyperfinite integer and let

$$X = \left\{ \frac{i}{H} : i = 0, 1, \dots, H \right\}.$$

Then “ $\{f(x) : x \in X\}$ is a * finite subset of ${}^*\mathbb{R}$ ” is true in *V . Since “every finite subset of \mathbb{R} has a maximal element” is true in V , then “every * finite subset of ${}^*\mathbb{R}$ has a maximal element” is true in *V . Let $r \in X$ be such that

$${}^*f(r) = \max\{f(x) : x \in X\}.$$

Let $c = st(r)$. Then $c \in [0, 1]$ and $f(c) \approx {}^*f(r)$ because f is continuous at c . For every $\beta \in [0, 1]$, there is $x \in X$ such that $x \approx \beta$. Hence $f(\beta) \approx f(x) \leq {}^*f(r) \approx f(c)$. Since $f(c)$ and $f(\beta)$ are standard, we have $f(\beta) \leq f(c)$. This shows that $f(c)$ is the maximum value of f on $[0, 1]$.

3. Connection Between Shnirel’man Density, Lower Asymptotic Density, and Upper Banach Density

In this section we introduce some applications of nonstandard methods to the problems involving upper Banach density. The results in this section are standard and are obtained by nonstandard methods. The common characteristic of the nonstandard proofs in this section is the use of Loeb measure spaces.

3.1. Loeb Measure Spaces

Definition 35 *An internal set Ω is called hyperfinite if $|\Omega|$, the cardinality of Ω in *V , is a hyperfinite integer.*

We construct a standard atomless complete countably additive probability space (Ω, Σ, μ_L) .

Definition 36 Let Ω be a hyperfinite set and $|\Omega| = H$. Let Σ_0 be the collection of all internal subsets of Ω . For each $A \in \Sigma_0$, let $\mu_0(A) = st(\frac{|A|}{H})$.

Exercise 37 Show that μ_0 is a standard finitely additive probability measure on Σ_0 .

Definition 38 For any subset X of Ω , internal or external, let

$$\bar{\mu}(X) = \inf\{\mu_0(A) : A \in \Sigma_0 \text{ and } A \supseteq X\},$$

$$\underline{\mu}(X) = \sup\{\mu_0(A) : A \in \Sigma_0 \text{ and } A \subseteq X\}.$$

Now define $\Sigma = \{X \subseteq \Omega : \bar{\mu}(X) = \underline{\mu}(X)\}$. For each $X \in \Sigma$ define $\mu_L(X) = \underline{\mu}(X)$. Then (Ω, Σ, μ_L) is called a hyperfinite Loeb probability space generated by the mormalized uniform counting measure, or simply a Loeb space. μ_L is called the Loeb measure on Ω (cf. [Lo]).

Theorem 39 1. $\Omega \in \Sigma$ and $\mu_L(\Omega) = 1$.

2. $\mu_L(\{x\}) = 0$ for each $x \in \Omega$.

3. Let $X \in \Sigma$ with $\mu_L(X) = 0$ and $Y \subseteq X$. Then $Y \in \Sigma$ and $\mu_L(Y) = 0$.

4. $X \in \Sigma$ iff For each standard $\epsilon > 0$ there exist internal sets A and B in Σ_0 such that $A \subseteq X \subseteq B$ and $\mu_L(B \setminus A) < \epsilon$.

5. If $X \in \Sigma$, then $\Omega \setminus X \in \Sigma$ and $\mu_L(\Omega \setminus X) = 1 - \mu_L(X)$.

6. If $X, Y \in \Sigma$ and $X \cap Y = \emptyset$, then $\mu_L(X \cup Y) = \mu_L(X) + \mu_L(Y)$.

7. Let $X \in \Sigma$. There exists $A \in \Sigma_0$ such that $\mu_L(X \Delta A) = 0$.

8. (Ω, Σ, μ_L) is a standard, atomless, countably additive, complete probability space.

Proof. (1)–(4) are direct consequences of the definitions. (5) and (6) are easy consequences of (4). We prove (7) and (8).

For (7) let $A_0 \subseteq A_1 \subseteq A_2 \subseteq \dots \subseteq X \subseteq \dots \subseteq B_2 \subseteq B_1 \subseteq B_0$ be such that $\mu_L(B_n \setminus A_n) < \frac{1}{n}$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$. For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let $F_n = \{A \in \Sigma_0 : A_n \subseteq A \subseteq B_n\}$. Then F_n is a nonempty internal set and $F_n \supseteq F_{n+1}$. By Theorem 26 there is $A \in \bigcap_{n \in \mathbb{N}} F_n$. Clearly $A_n \subseteq A \cap X$ and $A \cup X \subseteq B_n$ for each n . Hence $X \Delta A \subseteq B_n \setminus A_n$. This shows $\mu_L(X \Delta A) < \frac{1}{n}$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Hence $\mu_L(X \Delta A) = 0$.

For (8) the Loeb space is atomless because of (2) and complete because of (3). We need to show that Σ is a σ -algebra and μ_L is a countably additive measure on Σ .

Suppose $X_n \in \Sigma$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$. We show that $X = \bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} X_n \in \Sigma$.

Let ϵ be a standard positive real number. For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let $A_n \subseteq X_n \subseteq B_n$ be such that $\mu_L(B_n \setminus A_n) < \frac{\epsilon}{2^{n+1}}$. We want to find internal sets A, B such that $A \subseteq X \subseteq B$ and $\mu_L(B \setminus A) < \epsilon$. Let $\alpha = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \mu_L(\bigcup_{n=0}^k A_n)$ and let $K \in \mathbb{N}$ be large enough such that $A = \bigcup_{n=0}^K A_n$ has $\mu_L(A) > \alpha - \epsilon$. Note that A is internal. Let $S = \{k \in {}^*\mathbb{N} : |\bigcup_{n=0}^k B_n|/|\Omega| < \alpha + \epsilon\}$. Then S is internal by Lemma 23. For each standard k we have

$$|\bigcup_{n=0}^k B_n|/|\Omega| \leq \mu_L(\bigcup_{n=0}^k A_n) + \sum_{n=0}^k \frac{\epsilon}{2^{n+1}} < \alpha + \epsilon.$$

Hence $S \supseteq \mathbb{N}$. By Corollary 24, S contains a hyperfinite integer N . Let $B = \bigcup_{n=0}^N B_n$. Then $\mu_L(B \setminus A) < \alpha + \epsilon - \alpha + \epsilon = 2\epsilon$. Since ϵ is arbitrary, we have $X \in \Sigma$.

We now prove that μ_L is countably additive. Suppose $X_n \in \Sigma$ for each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ are pairwise disjoint. We show that $\mu_L(\bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} X_n) = \sum_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \mu_L(X_n)$.

For each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ we have $\sum_{n=0}^k \mu_L(X_n) = \mu_L(\bigcup_{n=0}^k X_n) \leq \mu_L(X) \leq 1$. Hence $\alpha = \sum_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \mu_L(X_n)$ exists. It suffices to show that $\mu_L(X) = \alpha$.

Given a standard $\epsilon > 0$, let $A_n \subseteq X_n \subseteq B_n$ be internal such that $\mu_L(B_n \setminus A_n) < \frac{\epsilon}{2^{n+1}}$. Again we can find a standard K with $A = \bigcup_{n=0}^K A_n$ and a hyperfinite N with $B = \bigcup_{n=0}^N B_n$ such that $\mu_L(A) > \alpha - \epsilon$ and $\mu_L(B) < \alpha + \epsilon$. Since $A \subseteq X \subseteq B$ we have

$$\alpha - \epsilon < \mu_L(X) < \alpha + \epsilon.$$

Since ϵ is arbitrary we have $\mu_L(X) = \alpha$. The ends the proof.

3.2. Densities of an Infinite Subset of \mathbb{N}

Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ and $x, y \in \mathbb{N}$. From now on $[x, y]$ will exclusively represent an interval of integers. Let $A(x, y) = |A \cap [x, y]|$ and $A(x) = A(1, x)$.

Definition 40

- *Shnirel'man density of A is defined by*

$$\sigma(A) = \inf_{x \geq 1} \frac{A(x)}{x}.$$

- *Lower asymptotic density of A is defined by*

$$\underline{d}(A) = \liminf_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{A(x)}{x}.$$

- Upper Banach density of A is defined by

$$BD(A) = \limsup_{x \rightarrow \infty} \sup_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{A(k, k+x)}{x+1}.$$

Clearly $0 \leq \sigma(A) \leq \underline{d}(A) \leq BD(A) \leq 1$ for all $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. Upper Banach density may not be as popular as Shnirel'man density and lower asymptotic density to number theorists. The following exercise gives a more descriptive definition of upper Banach density.

Exercise 41 Show that $BD(A) = \alpha$ iff α is the greatest number such that there exists a sequence of intervals $[a_n, b_n] \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ with

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (b_n - a_n) = \infty \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{A(a_n, b_n)}{b_n - a_n + 1} = \alpha.$$

We develop some relations between Shnirel'man density/lower asymptotic density and upper Banach density in the nonstandard model.

Lemma 42 Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ and $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$. If there is $x \in {}^*\mathbb{N}$ such that $\underline{d}({}^*A - x) \cap \mathbb{N} \geq \alpha$, then $BD(A) \geq \alpha$, where ${}^*A - x = \{a - x : a \in {}^*A\}$.

Proof. Let ϵ be a standard positive real number and $N \in \mathbb{N}$. It suffices to show that there is an interval $[a, b] \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$b - a > N \text{ and } \frac{A(a, b)}{b - a + 1} > \alpha - \epsilon.$$

Since $\underline{d}({}^*A - x) \cap \mathbb{N} \geq \alpha$, there is $k > N$ such that for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $n > k$ implies $\frac{{}^*A(x, x+n)}{n+1} > \alpha - \epsilon$. Let

$$X = \{n \in {}^*\mathbb{N} : n > k \text{ and } \frac{{}^*A(x, x+n)}{n+1} > \alpha - \epsilon\}.$$

Then X is internal and $\mathbb{N} \setminus [0, k] \subseteq X$. Hence X contains a hyperfinite integer H . So $\frac{{}^*A(x, x+H)}{H+1} > \alpha - \epsilon$. Let $\varphi(A, N, \alpha, \epsilon, \mathbb{N})$ be the formula

$$(\exists x, y \in \mathbb{N}) \left(y > N \wedge \frac{A(x, x+y)}{y+1} > \alpha - \epsilon \right).$$

Since $\varphi({}^*A, N, \alpha, \epsilon, {}^*\mathbb{N})$ is true in *V (H is a witness for y), then $\varphi(A, N, \alpha, \epsilon, \mathbb{N})$ is true in V , which implies the lemma.

The lemma above is one-sided. In order to derive a lemma for the other side we need to invoke the Birkhoff Ergodic Theorem. The proof of the theorem can be found, for example, in [Pe].

Birkhoff Ergodic Theorem *Let (Ω, μ) be a probability space and $T : \Omega \mapsto \Omega$ be a measure preserving transformation. For every $f \in L^1(\Omega)$, there is $\bar{f} \in L^1(\Omega)$ such that for μ -a.e. $x \in \Omega$,*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} f(T^k(x)) = \bar{f}(x).$$

Lemma 43 *Suppose $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ with $BD(A) = \alpha$. Let $[a_n, b_n] \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be such that*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (b_n - a_n) = \infty \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{A(a_n, b_n)}{b_n - a_n + 1} = \alpha.$$

If N is a hyperfinite integer and μ_L is the Loeb measure on the hyperfinite set $[a_N, b_N]$, then for μ_L -a.e. $x \in [a_N, b_N]$,

$$\underline{d}((^*A - x) \cap \mathbb{N}) = \alpha.$$

Proof. Following the Birkhoff Ergodic Theorem, let $\Omega = [a_N, b_N]$, $T(x) = x + 1$ for all $x \in [a_N, b_N - 1]$, $T(b_N) = a_N$, and $f = \chi_{^*A}$ be the characteristic function of the set $^*A \cap [a_N, b_N]$.

First, note that

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \chi_{^*A}(T^k(x)) = \frac{^*A(x, x + n - 1)}{n}$$

for all $x \in \bigcap_{n \in \mathbb{N}} [a_N, b_N - n]$. Second, note that $\underline{d}((^*A - x) \cap \mathbb{N}) \leq \alpha$ for all x because otherwise $BD(A) > \alpha$ by Lemma 42. Third, if there is a set of x with positive measure such that $\underline{d}((^*A - x) \cap \mathbb{N}) < \alpha$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= \mu_L(^*A \cap \Omega) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \int_{\Omega} \chi_{^*A}(T^k(x)) d\mu_L \\ &= \int_{\Omega} \left(\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \chi_{^*A}(T^k(x)) \right) d\mu_L = \int_{\Omega} \underline{d}((^*A - x) \cap \mathbb{N}) d\mu_L < \alpha. \end{aligned}$$

Hence we have $\underline{d}((^*A - x) \cap \mathbb{N}) = \alpha$, μ_L -a.e.

Lemma 44 *Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. If there is $x \in {}^*\mathbb{N}$ such that $\underline{d}((^*A - x) \cap \mathbb{N}) \geq \alpha$, then there is $y \in {}^*\mathbb{N}$ such that $\sigma((^*A - y) \cap \mathbb{N}) \geq \alpha$.*

Proof. Without loss of generality we can assume $\underline{d}(A) \geq \alpha$. For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ there is $a_n \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\sigma(A - a_n) \geq \alpha - \frac{1}{n}$. By Lemma 23 there is a hyperfinite $b_n \in {}^*\mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\min_{k \in [a_n+1, b_n]} \frac{^*A(a_n + 1, k)}{k} \geq \alpha - \frac{1}{n}.$$

Let $X = \{n \in {}^*\mathbb{N} : b_n - a_n > n \text{ and } \min_{k \in [a_n+1, b_n]} \frac{{}^*A(a_n+1, k)}{k} \geq \alpha - \frac{1}{n}\}$. Then X is internal and $\mathbb{N} \subseteq X$. Let $N \in X$ be hyperfinite. Then $b_N - a_N$ is hyperfinite and $\min_{k \in [a_N+1, b_N]} \frac{{}^*A(a_N+1, k)}{k} \geq \alpha - \frac{1}{N}$. Let $y = a_N$. Then we have $\sigma({}^*A - y) \cap \mathbb{N} \geq \alpha$.

From the lemmas above we can derive a theorem about upper Banach density parallel to each theorem about Shnirel'man density or lower asymptotic density. First we derive a theorem in [Ji2] parallel to Plünnecke's Theorem about Shnirel'man density (cf. [Na]). Most of the proof has already been done in detail in the lemmas above, so we need only to complete the proof in a few sentences.

Definition 45 A set $B \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ is called a basis of order h if $\underbrace{B + B + \cdots + B}_h = \mathbb{N}$ where

$$\underbrace{B + B + \cdots + B}_h = \{\sum_{i=1}^h b_i : b_i \in B\}.$$

Plünnecke's Theorem Let B be a basis of order h and $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. Then $\sigma(A+B) \geq \sigma(A)^{1-\frac{1}{h}}$.

Theorem 46 (Plünnecke's Theorem for BD) Let B be a basis of order h and $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. Then $BD(A + B) \geq BD(A)^{1-\frac{1}{h}}$.

Proof. Let $BD(A) = \alpha$. Choose $x \in {}^*\mathbb{N}$ such that $\sigma({}^*A - x) \cap \mathbb{N} = \alpha$. By Plünnecke's Theorem $\sigma({}^*(A + B) - x) \cap \mathbb{N} \geq \alpha^{1-\frac{1}{h}}$. Hence $BD(A + B) \geq \alpha^{1-\frac{1}{h}}$.

The idea of deriving a theorem about upper Banach density from an existing theorem about Shnirel'man density or lower asymptotic density should be clear now. We would like to challenge the reader to do a similar proof of the following result. The detailed proof can also be found in [Ji2].

Exercise 47 Mann's Theorem says that if 0 is in $A \cap B$, then $\sigma(A + B) \geq \sigma(A) + \sigma(B)$. Use the same idea as in the proof of Theorem 46 to prove that for any A and B

$$BD(A + B + \{0, 1\}) \geq BD(A) + BD(B).$$

Hint: It is helpful to visit van der Corput's Theorem (cf. [HR]).

Next, we derive a theorem parallel to Kneser's Theorem about lower asymptotic density. For a set A and a number g , let gA represent the set $\{ga : a \in A\}$.

Kneser's Theorem Let $A, B \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. If $\underline{d}(A + B) < \underline{d}(A) + \underline{d}(B)$, then there are $g > 0$ and $G \subseteq [0, g - 1]$ such that

1. $\underline{d}(A + B) \geq \underline{d}(A) + \underline{d}(B) - \frac{1}{g}$,
2. $A + B \subseteq G + g\mathbb{N}$, and
3. $(G + g\mathbb{N}) \setminus (A + B)$ is finite.

Exercise 48 Let $A, B \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be such that $BD(A + B) < BD(A) + BD(B)$. Prove that there exist $g \in \mathbb{N}$ and $G \subseteq [0, g - 1]$ and there exists a sequence of intervals $[a_n, b_n] \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (b_n - a_n) = \infty$ and

$$(A + B) \cap [a_n, b_n] = (a_n + G + g\mathbb{N}) \cap [a_n, b_n].$$

The proof of the exercise above involves only a small portion of A and B . We can derive a stronger version of that for $A + A$. The theorem below is a joint result of P. Bihani and the author (cf. [BJ]). The proof of the theorem is too long to be included in this article. So we give only a sketch of the idea.

Theorem 49 (Kneser’s Theorem for BD) Let $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. Suppose $BD(A + A) < 2BD(A)$ and $[a_n, b_n] \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ is a sequence of intervals such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (b_n - a_n) = \infty$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{A(a_n, b_n)}{b_n - a_n + 1} = BD(A)$. Then there are $g > 0$ and $G \subseteq [0, g - 1]$ such that

1. $BD(A + A) \geq 2BD(A) - \frac{1}{g}$,
2. $A + A \subseteq G + g\mathbb{N}$, and
3. there exist $[c_n, d_n] \subseteq [a_n, b_n]$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d_n - c_n}{b_n - a_n} = 1 \text{ and } (A + A) \cap [2c_n, 2d_n] = (G + g\mathbb{N}) \cap [2c_n, 2d_n].$$

Proof (sketch). Let $BD(A) = \alpha$. For each hyperfinite integer N the set ${}^*A \cap [a_N, b_N]$ is very “homogeneous” in $[a_N, b_N]$ in terms of the Loeb measure.

Let $S_N \subseteq [a_N, b_N]$ be the set of all x such that

$$\underline{d}({}^*A - x) \cap \mathbb{N} = \underline{d}(x - {}^*A) \cap \mathbb{N} = \alpha.$$

Then the Loeb measure of S_N in $[a_N, b_N]$ is 1. Let N and N' be two hyperfinite integers and let $x \in S_N$ and $y \in S_{N'}$. Applying Kneser’s theorem we can find the least $g_{x,y} > 0$ and $G_{x,y} \subseteq [0, g_{x,y} - 1]$ such that

$$({}^*A + {}^*A) \cap (x + y + \mathbb{Z}) = (G_{x,y} + g_{x,y} {}^*\mathbb{N}) \cap (x + y + \mathbb{Z}).$$

By some tedious work we can verify that $g_{x,y}$ and $G_{x,y}$ do not depend on x or y . Hence the structure of $*A + *A$ in each set $x + y + \mathbb{Z}$ can be put into a uniform structure in the set

$$\bigcup_{N \text{ is hyperfinite}} [a_N, b_N].$$

Then by the transfer principle we can derive the structural properties (1)–(3) of the theorem for $A + A$ in the set $\bigcup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} [a_n, b_n]$.

What prevents us from replacing $A + A$ by $A + B$? First of all we must consider two different sequences of intervals $[a_n^{(i)}, b_n^{(i)}]$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (b_n^{(i)} - a_n^{(i)}) = \infty$ for $i = 0, 1$,

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{A(a_n^{(0)}, b_n^{(0)})}{b_n^{(0)} - a_n^{(0)} + 1} = BD(A), \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B(a_n^{(1)}, b_n^{(1)})}{b_n^{(1)} - a_n^{(1)} + 1} = BD(B).$$

Then we consider the structure of $A + B$ in $[a_n^{(0)} + a_n^{(1)}, b_n^{(0)} + b_n^{(1)}]$. Because the length of $[a_n^{(0)}, b_n^{(0)}]$ and the length of $[a_n^{(1)}, b_n^{(1)}]$ may not be compatible, we may not get the structural property similar to (3) of Theorem 49. Besides this obstacle, we don't see other difficulties. The reader can find the proof of the following conjecture in author's preprint [Ji8].

Conjecture 50 *Let $A, B \subseteq \mathbb{N}$. Suppose $BD(A + B) < BD(A) + BD(B)$ and $[a_n^{(i)}, b_n^{(i)}] \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ for $i = 0, 1$ are two sequences of intervals such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} (b_n^{(i)} - a_n^{(i)}) = \infty$,*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{A(a_n^{(0)}, b_n^{(0)})}{b_n^{(0)} - a_n^{(0)} + 1} = BD(A), \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{B(a_n^{(1)}, b_n^{(1)})}{b_n^{(1)} - a_n^{(1)} + 1} = BD(B), \text{ and}$$

$$0 < \inf_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{b_n^{(0)} - a_n^{(0)}}{b_n^{(1)} - a_n^{(1)}} \leq \sup_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \frac{b_n^{(0)} - a_n^{(0)}}{b_n^{(1)} - a_n^{(1)}} < \infty.$$

Then there are $g > 0$ and $G \subseteq [0, g - 1]$ such that

1. $BD(A + B) \geq BD(A) + BD(B) - \frac{1}{g}$,
2. $A + B \subseteq G + g\mathbb{N}$, and
3. there exist $[c_n^{(i)}, d_n^{(i)}] \subseteq [a_n^{(i)}, b_n^{(i)}]$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d_n^{(i)} - c_n^{(i)}}{b_n^{(i)} - a_n^{(i)}} = 1$ for $i = 0, 1$ and for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

$$(A + B) \cap [c_n^{(0)} + c_n^{(1)}, d_n^{(0)} + d_n^{(1)}] = (G + g\mathbb{N}) \cap [c_n^{(0)} + c_n^{(1)}d_n^{(0)} + d_n^{(1)}].$$

4. Freiman's Inverse Problems with Small Doubling Constants

In this section we present an application of nonstandard methods to Freiman's inverse problems. The main tool of nonstandard methods is the cuts of non-negative integers. We first introduce some background information on Freiman's inverse problems.

4.1. Freiman’s Inverse Problems

During the late fifties and early sixties, G. Freiman obtained a series of results in additive/combinatorial number theory indicating that if $A + A$ is “small”, then A must have some arithmetic structure where A is a set of integers (cf. [Fr1], [Na]).

From now on A is a finite subset of \mathbb{N} and $|A| = k$. Suppose c is a constant independent of k . If $|A + A| \leq ck$, then we call c a doubling constant of A .

Let *a.p.* be an abbreviation for “arithmetic progression” and *b.p.* be an abbreviation for the union of two arithmetic progressions I and J with the same difference such that $I + I$, $I + J$, and $J + J$ are pairwise disjoint.

Freiman’s theorems have two different types. One type is for the sets A with a doubling constant being an arbitrary fixed number. The other type is for the sets A with a doubling constant between 2 and 3. The first type gives more general results but less accurate structures for A and the second type is less general but gives more accurate structures of A . Our interest is to generalize Freiman’s theorems of the second type in [Fr1].

Well-known Fact (1) If $|A| = k$, then $|A + A| \geq 2k - 1$. (2) If $|A + A| = 2k - 1$, then A is an a.p.

Freiman’s “Little” Theorem Let $|A| = k$.

1. If $k > 2$ and $|A + A| = 2k - 1 + b$ for $0 \leq b \leq k - 3$, then A is a subset of an a.p. of length $k + b$.
2. If $k > 6$ and $|A + A| = 3k - 3$, then A is either a subset of an a.p. of length $2k - 1$ or a b.p.
3. If $k > 10$ and $|A + A| = 3k - 2$, then A is either a subset of an a.p. of length $2k + 1$ or a subset of a b.p. of (combined) length $k + 1$.

The reader can see from the following examples that the results above are optimal

Example 51 1. Let $A = [0, k - 2] \cup \{k + b - 1\}$ for $k > 2$ and $b < k - 2$. Then $|A| = k$, $|A + A| = 2k - 1 + b$ and A is a subset of an a.p. of length $k + b$. Hence the upper bound of the length of a.p. containing A in (1) above is optimal.

2. Let $A = [0, k - 3] \cup \{k - 1, 2k - 2\}$ for $k > 6$. Then $|A + A| = 3k - 3$ and A is a subset of an a.p. of length $2k - 1$. Note that A is not a subset of a b.p. of a reasonable length. Let $A = [0, k - 2] \cup \{k^2\}$. Then $|A| = k$, $|A + A| = 3k - 3$, and A is a b.p. So (2) above is optimal.

For further generalization Freiman asked the following question in [Fr3] and [Fr2].

Freiman’s $3k - 3 + b$ Conjecture *There is a $K > 0$ such that if $|A| = k > K$ and $|A + A| = 3k - 3 + b$ for $0 \leq b \leq \frac{k}{3} - 3$, then A is either a subset of an a.p. of length $2k - 1 + 2b$ or a subset of a b.p. of length $k + b$.*

The following example shows that the upper bound for b in the conjecture above cannot be greater than $\frac{k}{3} - 3$.

Example 52 *Let $k = 3n$, $m > 2n$, and $A = [0, n - 1] \cup [m, m + n - 1] \cup [2m, 2m + n - 1]$. Then $|A| = k$, $|A + A| = 10n - 5 = 3k - 3 + \frac{k}{3} - 2$, and A is neither a subset of an a.p. of a reasonable length nor a subset of a b.p. of a reasonable length.*

Some work has been done on generalizing Freiman’s “little” theorem. For example, Hamidoune and Plagne [HP] characterized the structure of A when $|A - A| = 3|A| - 3$ and V. Lev [Le] proved that the Freiman’s conjecture is true when $A \subseteq [0, p]$, $0, p \in A$, p is a prime number, and $|A| < \frac{p}{35}$. In [LS] the sum $A + B$ is considered instead of $A + A$. Note that we haven’t found results similar to Freiman’s “little” theorem about the structure of A when the doubling constant of A is greater than 3. However, Kneser’s Theorem seems to give the structure of an infinite set A when the “doubling constant” of A is any constant less than 4.

Another Version of Kneser’s Theorem *Let $A, B \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ be infinite. If $\underline{d}(A + B) < \underline{d}(A) + \underline{d}(B)$, then there exist $g > 0$ and $F, F' \subseteq [0, g - 1]$ such that*

1. $A \subseteq F + g\mathbb{N}$ and $B \subseteq F' + g\mathbb{N}$
2. $\underline{d}(A) + \underline{d}(B) > \frac{|F| + |F'|}{g} - \frac{1}{g}$.

Exercise 53 *Prove that the version above is equivalent to Kneser’s Theorem in the second section.*

The version above indicates that if $B = A$ and $\underline{d}(A + A) < 2\underline{d}(A)$, then A is a large subset of the union of $|F|$ a.p.’s of difference g .

Note that in Freiman’s “little” theorem, the structure can be pinpointed only when the doubling constant is ≤ 3 . However, if A is infinite, then either A has a nice arithmetic structure or $\underline{d}(A + A) \geq 2\underline{d}(A)$, which implies that we can find an increasing sequence a_n such that $(A + A)(2a_n) \geq (4 - \epsilon)A(a_n)$ for an arbitrary $\epsilon > 0$. By using a cut in nonstandard methods we can apply Kneser’s Theorem to a significant portion of A .

4.2. Nonstandard Cuts

Definition 54 An infinite proper initial segment U of ${}^*\mathbb{N}$ is called a cut if $U + U \subseteq U$.

We often write $n < U$ for $n \in U$ and write $n > U$ for $n \in {}^*\mathbb{N} \setminus U$.

Example 55 \mathbb{N} is the smallest cut. Let H be a hyperfinite integer. Then

$$U_H = \bigcap_{n \in \mathbb{N}} [0, \frac{H}{n}]$$

is the largest cut below H .

Note that if $x < U_H$, then $\frac{x}{H} \approx 0$; if $x > U_H$, then $\frac{x}{H} > \epsilon$ for some standard positive ϵ .

Theorem 56 Let U be a cut and $A \subseteq {}^*\mathbb{N}$ be internal.

1. Suppose $g \in \mathbb{N}$ and $G \subseteq [0, g - 1]$. If $A \cap U \subseteq G + g \cdot {}^*\mathbb{N}$, then there is $H > U$ such that $A \cap [0, H] \subseteq G + g \cdot \mathbb{N}$.
2. Let $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$. Suppose for every $x \in U$ there is y with $x < y < U$ such that $\frac{(A+A)(y)}{y} \geq \alpha$. Then there is $H > U$ such that $\frac{(A+A)(H)}{H} \geq \alpha$.

Proof. By Lemma 23.

Definition 57 Let U be a cut and $A \subseteq {}^*\mathbb{N}$ be internal. The lower U -density of A is defined by

$$\underline{d}_U(A) = \sup \left\{ \inf \left\{ st \left(\frac{A(x)}{x} \right) : m < x < U \right\} : m < U \right\}.$$

Note that for $A \subseteq \mathbb{N}$ we have $\underline{d}_{\mathbb{N}}({}^*A) = \underline{d}(A)$.

From now on we are only interested in the cuts of the form U_H for some hyperfinite integer H . When H is clearly given, we will drop the subscript H and simply write U for U_H .

4.3. Main Application

The following lemma is a key to applying Kneser’s Theorem to Freiman’s inverse problem. The proof of the lemma is too long to be included in this article. The reader can find the proof in [Ji5].

Lemma 58 *Let H be hyperfinite and $A \subseteq [0, H]$ be internal such that $0 \in A$ and $0 < \underline{d}_U(A) = \alpha < \frac{2}{3}$. Then one of the following is true.*

1. *There is $g > 1$ such that $A \cap U \subseteq gU$.*
2. *There are $g > 1$ and $a \in [1, g - 1]$ with $2a \neq g$ such that $A \cap U \subseteq gU \cup (a + gU)$.*
3. *There is a positive standard real ϵ such that for every $x < U$, there is $y \in A$ with $x < y < U$ and $\frac{(A+A)(2y)}{2y} \geq \frac{3}{2}\alpha + \epsilon$.*

Lemma 58 is a weak version of Kneser’s theorem for U . Using Lemma 58 we are able to prove the following generalization of Freiman’s “little” theorem. The proof of the following generalization is again too long to be included in this article. We describe only the brief idea of the proof. The reader can find the complete proof in [Ji6].

Theorem 59 *There exist $K \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\epsilon \in \mathbb{R}$, $\epsilon > 0$, such that if $|A| = k > K$ and $|A + A| = 3k - 3 + b$ for $0 \leq b \leq \epsilon k$, then A is either a subset of an a.p. of length $2k - 1 + 2b$ or A is a subset of a b.p. of length $k + b$.*

Ideas of Proof. **First Step:** Suppose the theorem is not true. For each $n \in \mathbb{N}$ there is a counter-example A_n with $|A_n| = k_n > n$ and

$$|A_n + A_n| - 3k_n - 3 < \frac{1}{n}k_n.$$

Let N be a hyperfinite integer and $A = A_N$ be a counter-example of the theorem with $|A|$ being hyperfinite and $\frac{|A+A|}{|A|} \approx 3$. Without loss of generality we can assume $0 = \min A$, $H = \max A$, $\gcd(A) = 1$, and $st\left(\frac{|A|}{H+1}\right) = \alpha > 0$. Note that $\alpha \leq \frac{1}{2}$. We can also assume that α is the least number such that there is a hyperfinite counter-example of the theorem $A \subseteq [0, H]$ for some hyperfinite number H with $0, H \in A$, $\gcd(A) = 1$, and $st\left(\frac{|A|}{H+1}\right) = \alpha$.

Second Step: Let $\beta = \underline{d}_U(A)$.

Case 1: $\beta \geq \frac{2}{3}$. Then there are $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $N > U$ in A such that $[n, N] \subseteq A + A$ and $st\left(\frac{A(N,H)}{H-N+1}\right) < \alpha$. One can now find the structural information for the part $A \cap [N, H]$, which allow us to derive a contradiction to the assumption that $\frac{|A+A|}{|A|} \approx 3$.

Case 2: $0 < \beta < \frac{2}{3}$. Then either (a) A has nice arithmetic structure in $[0, N]$ for some $N > U$ in A , or (b) $(A + A)(2N) \geq (3 + \epsilon)A(N)$ for some $N > U$ in A . If (a) is true, then we have a pan-handle to start a tedious verification process that A has the desired structure, which it is not assumed to have. If (b) is true, then we can derive the conclusion that $\frac{|A+A|}{|A|} \geq 3 + \epsilon$ for some positive standard ϵ , which again leads to a contradiction.

Case 3: $\beta = 0$. Then we can consider the lower U -density of A from the right end of an interval $[0, N]$ for some $N > U$ in A instead.

In Case 2 we use the fact that in the nonstandard model a hyperfinite interval $[0, H]$ contains the cut $U = U_H$ similar to \mathbb{N} . If the part of A in U has a doubling constant greater than 3, then we can conclude that the doubling constant of A is greater than 3. Otherwise, $A \cap U$ has the desired structure, which implies that A has the desired structure. Can this idea be applied to solve Freiman's $3k - 3 + b$ conjecture? Before we can succeed, we need to improve Lemma 58 first so that the lemma can be applied to the case when the doubling constant is between 3 and $\frac{10}{3}$. The following improvement of Lemma 58 has recently been obtained in [Ji7].

Lemma 60 *Let H be hyperfinite and $U = U_H \subseteq [0, H]$. Let $A \subseteq [0, H]$ be internal. Suppose $0 \in A$ and $0 < \underline{d}_U(A) = \alpha < \frac{3}{5}$. If for all sufficiently large $x \in A \cap U$ we have*

$$\frac{(A + A)(2x)}{2x} \lesssim \frac{5}{3} \cdot \frac{A(x)}{x},$$

then one of the following must be true:

1. $A \cap U$ is a subset of an a.p. of difference $g > 1$ and $\alpha \geq \frac{3}{5g}$.
2. $A \cap U$ is a subset of a b.p. of the form $\{0, a\} + gU$ with some $g > 2$ and $a \in [1, g - 1]$ such that $\alpha \geq \frac{2}{(1+\beta)g}$ where

$$\beta = \inf \left\{ \gamma : \text{for all sufficiently large } x \in A \right. \\ \left. \frac{(A + A)(2x)}{2x} \lesssim (3 + \gamma) \cdot \frac{A(x)}{x} \right\}.$$

3. $A \cap U$ is a subset of $\{0, a_1, a_2\} + gU$, where $g > 4$, $a_1 < a_2$ in $[1, g - 1]$, and the set $\{0, a_1, a_2\} + \{0, a_1, a_2\}$ modulo g contains 5 elements, such that $\alpha = \frac{3}{g}$.

Using the result above we hope to prove the following weak version of Freiman's $3k - 3 + b$ conjecture first.

Weak Conjecture *There is $K \in \mathbb{N}$ such that for any $0 < c < \frac{1}{3}$ and any A with $|A| = k > K$ and $|A + A| = 3k - 3 + b$ for $0 \leq b \leq ck$, A is either a subset of an a.p. of length $2k - 1 + 2b$ or a subset of a b.p. of length $k + b$.*

If the conjecture above is confirmed, then the solution for Freiman's $3k - 3 + b$ conjecture would not be far from reach.

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